

Guardians of the Nation: A Study of Psychological Resilience of Frontline Soldiers at the Indo-China Border

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Soldiers deployed in high-altitude border areas face many environmental and operational challenges that require significant psychological resilience. The current study intended to assess psychological resilience among Indian Army soldiers posted in the high-altitude, sensitive, and remote areas of Uttarakhand. Data were collected using convenience sampling from 60 male soldiers during the "Ranbhoomi Darshan" program, conducted by Hemvati Nandan Bahuguna Garhwal University in collaboration with the Garhwal Rifles Regimental Centre, Lansdowne, in October 2025. The program was conducted with Indian Army soldiers deployed in high-altitude areas along the India-China border of Uttarakhand. Resilience was measured using the Resilience Scale developed by Laxmi and Narain (2017). The findings show a high level of overall psychological resilience among Indian Army soldiers deployed in the high-altitude border areas of Uttarakhand, which suggests that soldiers deployed along the Uttarakhand border have an extraordinary ability to bounce back, manage stress, and overcome adversity. This resilience likely serves as a vital psychological buffer.

Keywords: Resilience, military psychology, strength, positive psychology

Resilience is the ability of an individual to successfully overcome adversity and life challenges (APA, 2018). A resilient individual stays calm in distressing situations and uses their skills and strength to cope with adversity. The term "Resilience" originates from the Latin word *resilire*, meaning "to leap back." Oxford Dictionary of English defines resilience as "the ability to withstand or recover from difficult conditions" (Soanes & Stevenson, 2006).

Soldiers are the first line of national security across the border. Every day, they face a wide range of stressful events and hardships during training and active field operations (Wijk, 2024). Generally, soldiers are deployed in high-risk border areas where they face challenging environmental and psychological conditions, including high-altitude challenges (harsh cold, low oxygen levels), limited family and social support, and constant proximity to potential conflict. These circumstances place significant demands on high psychological functioning and

adaptive capacity (Kumar, 2025). Therefore, the ability to adapt to risky and threatening situations is not only important but also a survival skill for them.

In a previous study, Rice and Liu (2016) reported that high resilience was observed among active military personnel, particularly those with higher levels of education. Psychological resilience is significant in strengthening mental health (Wijk, 2024) by reducing psychological symptoms of poor mental health (Cao et al., 2023). Furthermore, resilience is positively associated with overall well-being and successful adjustment to military life, and it serves as a crucial buffer against stress (Ha & Jue, 2022; Kanapeckaitė & Bagdžiūnienė, 2024). Resilience is also entwined with interpersonal and organisational factors. Resilient soldiers demonstrate greater organisational commitment, a trait actively fostered by and highly correlated with strong team cohesion and peer support (Ha & Jue, 2022; Kanapeckaitė & Bagdžiūnienė, 2024). Kanapeckaitė et al. (2022) reported that higher psychological resilience directly predicted greater effort, proactivity, self-efficacy, and perceived military competencies among reserve soldiers.

There is a lack of research focusing on Indian Army soldiers deployed in the extremely high-altitude border areas. The current study aims to address this gap by providing preliminary evidence on psychological resilience among frontline soldiers deployed along the Indo-China border in Uttarakhand. The findings aim to contribute meaningfully to the design of psychological support and resilience-building programmes for soldiers.

Objective of the Study

The objective of the present study is

- To study the level of resilience among soldiers deployed in the Indo-China border areas of Uttarakhand,
- To study the levels of different dimensions of resilience among soldiers deployed in the border area

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Method

Participants

The data were collected using convenience sampling during the “*Ranbhoomi Darshan*” program conducted by Hemvati Nandan Bahuguna Garhwal University in collaboration with the Garhwal Rifles Regimental Centre, Lansdown. They organised a visit to the Indo-China border areas in October 2025. The present study comprised 60 Indian Army soldiers (aged 19-35) deployed in high-altitude areas along the India-China border in Malari village, Niti and Mana Valley, and Badrinath, Uttarakhand.

Research Design

This study adopted a descriptive research design because there is a lack of prior empirical data on this population.

Measure

Resilience scale: This scale was developed by Laxmi and Narain (2014) to assess an individual's ability to adapt and recover from adversity. It is a 30-item scale that measures four dimensions of resilience. It includes 8 items of perseverance, 9 of composure, 7 of self-reliance, and 6 of faith. It is suitable for individuals aged 14 years and above. It has test-retest reliability of 0.87 and split-half reliability of 0.84. It also has a high validity. It is a 5-point Likert scale scoring from 'Strongly Agree', 'Agree', 'Neutral', 'Disagree' and 'Strongly Disagree'. Scoring below 84 indicates a low level of resilience; scores between 84 and 122 are considered average; and scores 122 and above signify a high level of resilience.

Procedure

During the *Ranbhoomi darshan* program, a visit to the border areas of Uttarakhand near China, the resilience questionnaire was separately administered to 60 selected participants. They were presented with the concept of resilience, its related dimensions, and their importance to defence personnel. They were also informed regarding the purpose of the current research study. Also, they were assured of the confidentiality of their identities and the responses they provided.

Statistical Analysis

The collected data were analysed and presented in accordance with

the objectives outlined in this study, using descriptive statistics.

Results

The current study aims to assess resilience among soldiers deployed in highly sensitive, remote areas along the India-China border near Malari village, Niti and Mana Valley, and Badrinath, Uttarakhand.

All participants are male, aged 19-35, with an average age of 24.81 years and a SD of 4.20. Most participants are highly educated, with the majority holding a Bachelor's degree (Table 1).

Table 1

Demographic Details

Demographic Details		
Age	19-35	24.81 (Mean)
Education	12th	25
	BA	23
	BBA	01
	BCA	01
	BSc	10
Sex	Male Only	
	Total (N)	60

Table 2 shows that participants' overall resilience scores ranged from 103 (minimum) to 138 (maximum). The median resilience score for all participants is 124.5, with a mean of 122.82 and an SD of 7.68. According to the normative distribution (scores < 84 = low, 84-122 = medium, ≥ 122 = high), the scale's mean score falls within the strong resilience range. This shows that soldiers in the present study have a strong ability to adjust to and overcome adversity.

A skewness value of -0.453 and a kurtosis value of -0.17 suggested that the score distribution was approximately symmetric. The majority of participants scored at or above the resilience threshold; the slight negative skew suggests a small cluster of scores at the lower end of the distribution. Although the middle 50% of scores fall between 117.75 (Q1) and 127.25 (Q3), with an interquartile range (IQR) of 9.5, this indicates relatively low variability and consistency in resilience scores of all participants (Table 2).

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics of Overall Resilience

Descriptive statistics												
N	Mean	Median	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis	Range	Variance	SE	Q1	Q3	IQR	
60	122.81	124.5	±7.68	-0.453	-0.17	35	59	0.99	117.75	127.25	9.5	

Note. Result - High Resilience

Table 3

Mean and SD on Dimensions of Resilience

Dimensions	Perseverance	Composure	Self-reliance	Faith
Mean	32.62	37.76	25.88	26.55
SD	±2.71	±2.57	±2.28	±2.83
Level	High	High	High	High

Table 3 shows a consistently high level of resilience across all four dimensions among the soldiers.

The mean score indicates soldiers have high Composure (37.76), followed by Perseverance (32.62), Faith (26.55), and Self-reliance (25.88). The Standard deviation reflects less deviation, indicating consistency and homogeneity across all dimensions of resilience (Figure 1).

Figure 1*Graphical Representation of Resilience Dimensions*

Discussion

It has become an important ability for soldiers, as previous studies suggest that resilience training is associated with lower stress and higher well-being (Niederhauser et al., 2023). Also, it acts as a protective factor during hardships and improves performance (Sefidan et al., 2021). The current study primarily assesses the level of psychological resilience among Indian Army soldiers deployed in high-altitude, border areas of Uttarakhand. The finding shows that a significant proportion (58%) of participants with Bachelor's degrees reported that higher levels of education are associated with greater resilience, aligning with Wijk's (2024) previous finding. Similar to Rice and Liu (2016) the findings also indicate that participants possess a high level of overall resilience (Mean = 122.81), which surpasses the threshold for "strong resilience" (≥ 122) according to the normative criteria of the resilience scale (Table 2). This elevated resilience can be attributed to the demanding nature of the military profession. The finding of the current study is the consistently high scores across all four dimensions, i.e. Perseverance, Composure, Self-reliance, and Faith. Perseverance (Mean = 32.62) suggests a strong capacity to manage and persevere in the face of adversity. Composure (Mean = 37.76) suggests calm in distressing situations. Self-reliance (25.88) and Faith (26.55) reflect confidence in one's judgment and a belief in personal capability. It provides psychological stability in remote border regions.

Conclusion

The current study provides compelling evidence of a high level of psychological resilience among Indian Army soldiers deployed in the high-altitude, sensitive border areas of Uttarakhand. It also reveals that soldiers' mean scores are high across all four dimensions of resilience, suggesting they have a powerful ability to manage stress and regulate emotions, as well as determination, persistence, trust in their judgement, and the ability to navigate challenges. This profile provides a psychologically resilient and supportive individual, capable of facing the challenges of deployment in

difficult border regions.

Limitations and Recommendations

Each study has its limitations. The current study has a small sample size, which does not accurately represent the entire Indian Army. In addition, there is no gender representation, as all participants were male. The current study lays the foundation for policy-making regarding the welfare of soldiers. We encourage future investigation of a large and diverse population and recommend the use of different research methods.

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